

Protocol

Initial study with a national online panel: Exploring participant motivations and preferences

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Background

In October and November 2024 the Centre for Epidemic Intervention Research at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) established “FHI-panelet” (FHI is the acronym for Folkehelseinstituttet; NIPH-panel). The aim of the panel is to facilitate research (including online trials and surveys) on how to communicate health research and advice during health crises, in addition to having a pool of potential participants for research related to Public Health and Social Measures. Such panels are increasingly common, however, there are few national panels as large as the FHI-panel. Understanding panel members’ motives for participation is not only important when considering the types of surveys and studies to implement, but also participant retention and compliance with invitations to surveys/studies(1). There may be numerous reasons why people choose to take part in online panels, and what motivates them to continue their membership. Previous literature indicates that a person is motivated to join an online panel because of a moral obligation (participate in research to improve society), an interest in the topic, the desire for personal growth or improving self-knowledge (2), or in some cases monetary incentives(3).

There is no consensus regarding “best practice” for public health communication from authorities during health crises (4-8). There are numerous rubrics by which “good” communication can be measured, including those related to (a) how something is communicated (simple language, clear messages, communication of uncertainty), (b) what is communicated (advice, consequences, fact-checking), (c) when something is communicated (timing), and (d) to whom the message is communicated (key demographic groups, etc). Furthermore, a variety of specific metrics and factors must be carefully evaluated, including audience demographics, message clarity, channel effectiveness, engagement rates, and overall alignment with organizational goals. Both parameters and metrics for assessing good communication are well researched, and a recent literature review identified the following three strategies that are considered most effective during health crisis communication: fact based, transparent messages, people-centered persuasive techniques, and consistent messaging using international and/or cross-sector collaboration(9). In this study, we aim to explore what the panel prioritizes regarding health crisis communication from public health authorities in order to inform future studies concerning communication of health research.

Objectives

The objective of this study is to better understand the preferences and needs of Norwegian adults related to health crisis communication. The specific aims are to:

1. Identify motivations and preferences of Norwegian adults for participating in the online panel
2. Explore the preferred components of communication by authorities during a health crisis

Methods

Study design

This is an online cross-sectional survey using the FHI-panelet, and Nettskjema survey software to collect responses.

Participant recruitment and selection

We will invite 22 000 Norwegian panel members to participate in the study via email. Participants will be informed of the goal of the study. Consent for using collected data on demographics has already been established via the participation in the panel, and participation in the online survey is subsequent confirmation of participation in *this* study. Participants will be informed that by responding to the survey they consent to the use of their data for this project (see appendix 1 for the Consent form). All panel members (Norwegian adults 16 years and older) will be eligible for participation.

Panel members will receive an invitation to participate in the survey via email.

Statistical analysis and sample size calculation

We are not testing any specific hypotheses, so no sample size calculation has been carried out.

Survey

Questionnaire

The survey includes in total 7 multiple choice questions divided into 3 sections: 4 questions on motivation and interests regarding panel participations, 2 questions on communication and one question on preferences regarding advice provided by governments. All of the included questions are intended to assess attitudes/preferences and participants will be asked to select up to two predefined statements that best describe their preference/motivation/attitude. A copy of the questionnaire can be found in appendix 1. The questions are weighted equally. The questions have not been validated, however, the survey questions have been user-tested and has an estimated completion time of 3 to 7 minutes.

Data collection

Demographic covariates

Participants consented to having some of their personal data stored when they joined the panel (sex, date of birth, address, marital status, country of birth). They also reported their highest education level and household size. In this study we will use the following covariates in analysis:

- Sex
- Age
- Country of birth
- Highest education level
- Geographic region

Ethical considerations

We will seek consent from all participants. The Regional Ethics Committee of South-East Norway (REC) has deemed the project to fall outside the scope of health research so the project does not need ethical approval.

Data analysisThe data will be anonymised before beginning with data analysis. We will analyse data quality checks to exclude invalid responses before beginning analysis.

We will use descriptive analysis to summarize the demographic characteristics of the study population. Categorical variables will be presented using frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables will be presented using means and standard deviations.

For single-choice responses, we will report frequencies and the percentage of respondents selecting each statement. For multiple-choice responses, we will report the results as a percentage of the total number of choices to show how often each option was selected overall, as well as a percentage of the respondents to illustrate the proportion of participants who chose each option.

Missing responses

If respondents have not indicated a preference for a statement, we will treat them as not having any preference, but they will be counted towards the total number of participants

Non-respondent bias

We will compare demographic covariates across responders and the full panel. For comparing continuous variables, we will use t-tests. For categorical variables, we will use the Chi-Square Test. For binary variables, we will use the Z-test for two proportions.

Data Visualization

We will use visualizations such as bar charts, pie charts, and histograms to effectively present the results.

Software/Tools

The analysis will be conducted using R and R Studio.

Further analysis

If further analyses beyond descriptive statistics are deemed necessary, they will be prespecified in a detailed statistical analysis plan.

Funding

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References

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Appendix 1: Translated consent form and questionnaire

Norwegian	English
<p>Takk for din interesse til å delta. Du har fått invitasjonen fordi du meldte deg inn i FHI-panelet. For mer informasjon kan du besøke våre nettsider. Senter for forskning på epidemiltak ved Folkehelseinstituttet er ansvarlig for kartleggingen. Formålet med undersøkelsen er å få bedre kunnskap om deltakerne i FHI-panelet. Vi spør også om hvordan du finner fram til helseinformasjon og hvordan du foretrekker at myndighetene kommuniserer under pandemier. Hvis du velger å delta i kartleggingen, innebærer det at du fyller ut et spørreskjema, som tar ca 3-7 minutter. Ved å gjennomføre samtykker du til at vi lagrer dine data til prosjektslutt, satt til 1. desember 2027. Det er frivillig å delta. Hvis du velger å delta, kan du når som helst trekke samtykket tilbake uten å oppgi noen grunn. Alle dine personopplysninger vil da bli slettet. Det vil ikke ha noen negative konsekvenser for deg hvis du ikke vil delta eller senere velger å trekke deg. Du trekker deg fra kartleggingen ved å sende en epost til fhi-panelet@fhi.no</p> <p>Ditt personvern – hvordan vi oppbevarer og bruker opplysningene dine</p> <p>Vi vil bare bruke opplysningene om deg til formålene vi har fortalt om her. Vi behandler opplysningene konfidensielt og i samsvar med personvernregelverket. Dine data vil lagres i tjenester for sensitive data (TSD), som er et sikkert prosjektområde for forskningsdata. Kun to forskere ved FHI (Ingeborg Hess Elgersma og Christine Holst) vil ha tilgang til dette området. Du kan lese mer om hvordan vi behandler dine personlige data her</p> <p>Dine rettigheter</p> <p>Så lenge du kan identifiseres i datamaterialet, har du rett til: innsyn i hvilke opplysninger vi behandler om deg, og å få utlevert en kopi av opplysningene å få rettet opplysninger om deg som er feil eller misvisende å få slettet personopplysninger om deg å sende klage til Datatilsynet om behandlingen av dine personopplysninger Har du andre spørsmål til prosjektet eller ønsker å vite mer om eller benytte deg av dine rettigheter ta kontakt med fhi-panelet@fhi.no. Ingeborg Hess Elgersma er prosjektleder for denne kartleggingen. Hvis du har spørsmål knyttet til vurderingen som er</p>	<p>Thank you for your interest in participating. You have received this invitation because you joined the FHI panel. For more information, you can visit our websites. Centre for Epidemic Intervention Research at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health is responsible for the survey. The purpose of the survey is to gain better knowledge about the participants in the FHI panel. We also ask about how you find health information and how you prefer the authorities to communicate during pandemics. If you choose to participate in the survey, it involves filling out a questionnaire, which takes approximately 3-7 minutes. By completing it, you consent to us storing your data until the end of the project, set to December 1, 2027. Participation is voluntary. If you choose to participate, you can withdraw your consent at any time without providing any reason. All your personal data will then be deleted. There will be no negative consequences for you if you do not wish to participate or later choose to withdraw. You can withdraw from the survey by sending an email to fhi-panelet@fhi.no.</p> <p>Your privacy – how we store and use your information We will only use the information about you for the purposes mentioned here. We handle the information confidentially and in accordance with privacy regulations. Your data will be in services for sensitive data (TSD), which is a secure project area for research data. Only two researchers at FHI (Ingeborg Hess Elgersma and Christine Holst) will have access to this area. You can read more about how we process your personal data here.</p> <p>Your rights</p> <p>As long as you can be identified in the data material, you have the right to: access the information we process about you and obtain a copy of the information, correct information about you that is incorrect or misleading, delete personal information about you, complain to the Data Inspectorate about the processing of your personal data. If you have other questions about the project or wish to learn more about or exercise your rights, contact fhi-panelet@fhi.no. Ingeborg Hess Elgersma is the project leader for this survey. If you have questions related to the privacy assessment</p>

<p>gjort av personvernet i dette prosjektet kan du ta kontakt med personvernombud@fhi.no.</p> <p>Hva gir oss rett til å behandle personopplysninger om deg?</p> <p>Vi behandler opplysninger om deg basert på ditt samtykke.</p> <p>Ved å trykke på "Neste side" godtar du vilkårene. Vi setter stor pris deltagelsen din!</p>	<p>conducted in this project, you can contact personvernombud@fhi.no.</p> <p>What gives us the right to process personal data about you?</p> <p>We process information about you based on your consent.</p> <p>By clicking "Next page," you agree to the terms. We greatly appreciate your participation!</p>
<p>Fyll inn din personlige kode som du fikk i e-posten fra oss. Denne koden skriver du inn i spørreskjemaet for å komme videre og være med i trekning av gavekort.</p>	<p>Enter your personal code that you received in the email from us. You enter this code in the questionnaire to proceed and participate in the gift card draw.</p>
<p>Hva er de viktigste grunnene for at du ble med i FHI-panelet?</p> <p>Velg opp til to alternativ</p> <p>Å få ny kunnskap og innsikt</p> <p>Å bidra med mine synspunkt</p> <p>Å vinne premier</p> <p>Å bidra til samfunnsnyttig forskning</p> <p>Å lære mer om hvordan forskning foregår</p>	<p>What are the main reasons you joined the FHI panel?</p> <p>Choose up to two options</p> <p>To gain new knowledge and insights</p> <p>To contribute my viewpoints</p> <p>To win prizes</p> <p>To contribute to socially beneficial research</p> <p>To learn more about how research is conducted</p>
<p>Er det andre grunner for at du ble med i FHI-panelet?</p>	<p>Are there other reasons you joined the FHI panel?</p>
<p>Tenk deg at du har fått en alvorlig sykdom. Hvordan ville du ha søkt etter informasjon om hvordan denne sykdommen kan behandles?</p> <p>Velg opp til to alternativ</p> <p>Jeg ville ha googlet</p> <p>Jeg ville ha lett etter studier som sammenligner forskjellige typer behandling</p> <p>Jeg ville ha spurt fastlegen eller annet helsepersonell</p> <p>Jeg ville ha rådført meg med familie og venner</p> <p>Jeg ville ha lett på sosiale media</p> <p>Jeg ville ha hørt med andre som har hatt sykdommen</p>	<p>Imagine that you have been diagnosed with a serious illness. How would you seek information on how this illness can be treated?</p> <p>Choose up to two options</p> <p>I would google it</p> <p>I would look for studies comparing different types of treatment</p> <p>I would ask my general practitioner or other healthcare professionals</p> <p>I would consult with family and friends</p> <p>I would search on social media</p> <p>I would ask others who have had the illness</p>
<p>Hvis du ville søkt etter informasjon på en annen måte, beskriv dette gjerne her</p>	<p>If you would seek information in another way, please describe it here.</p>
<p>Hvilke av følgende elementer anser du som viktigst for kommunikasjon fra helsemyndigheter og/eller regjeringen under en pandemi?</p> <p>Velg opp til tre alternativ</p> <p>At informasjonen er faktasjekket, pålitelig og vitenskapelig forankret</p> <p>At man er åpen om usikkerhet om effekten av tiltak</p> <p>Tydelige og enkle budskap</p> <p>Hyppige oppdateringer om hvordan situasjonen utvikler seg</p> <p>Klare råd om hvordan den enkelte kan beskytte seg mot å bli smittet</p>	<p>Which of the following elements do you consider most important for communication from health authorities and/or the government during a pandemic?</p> <p>Choose up to three options</p> <p>That the information is fact-checked, reliable, and scientifically based</p> <p>Being transparent about uncertainties regarding the effectiveness of measures</p> <p>Clear and simple messages</p> <p>Frequent updates on how the situation is developing</p> <p>Clear advice on how individuals can protect themselves from infection</p>

<p>Informasjon om pandemiens konsekvenser for den enkelte og for samfunnet</p>	<p>Information about the pandemic's consequences for individuals and for society</p>
<p>Gitt at en studie tar følgende tid å gjennomføre, hvor ofte tror du at du takker ja til å delta i studier i regi av FHI-panelet?</p> <p>1 - 5 minutter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aldri • 1 gang i året • 2 ganger i året • 3 eller flere ganger i året • Vet ikke <p>5 - 15 minutter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aldri • 1 gang i året • 2 ganger i året • 3 eller flere ganger i året • Vet ikke <p>15 - 40 minutter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aldri • 1 gang i året • 2 ganger i året • 3 eller flere ganger i året • Vet ikke 	<p>Given that a study takes the following amount of time to complete, how often do you think you would agree to participate in studies conducted by the FHI panel?</p> <p>1 - 5 minutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never • Once a year • Twice a year • Three or more times a year • Don't know <p>5 - 15 minutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never • Once a year • Twice a year • Three or more times a year • Don't know <p>15 - 40 minutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never • Once a year • Twice a year • Three or more times a year • Don't know
<p>Hva synes du er en god premiering av det å delta i studier i FHI-panelet?</p> <p>At mange får gavekort på 2000 kr. At noen få får gavekort på 4000 kr.</p>	<p>What do you think is a good reward for participating in studies in the FHI panel?</p> <p>That many people receive gift cards worth 2000 kr. That a few people receive gift cards worth 4000 kr.</p>
<p>Har du andre innspill til gode premier for å delta i FHI-panelet?</p>	<p>Do you have any other suggestions for good rewards for participating in the FHI panel?</p>
<p>Takk for at du deltok i denne undersøkelsen. Har du innspill til spørsmålene du fikk eller noe du synes vi burde gjøre annerledes i fremtidige studier?</p>	<p>Thank you for participating in this survey. Do you have any feedback on the questions you received or suggestions for what we could do differently in future studies?</p>